

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Adapting law enforcement agencies to new security challenges in Nepal

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World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2024, 23(03), 575–584

Publication history: Received on 26 July 2024; revised on 01 September 2024; accepted on 04 September 2024

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.23.3.2694>

Abstract

In today's complex security landscape, the focus on maintaining a robust military-like discipline among paramilitary and the security forces have overshadowed the traditional roles of having enforced the law through authority institutions. These agencies have been tasked with mitigating various dynamic security threats. Contemporary security perspectives are increasingly shaped by challenges such as terrorism, migration, armed conflicts, and the activities of non-state entities, which are prevalent across nations. The rise in extremism, armed conflicts, insurgencies, civil wars, cyber threats, and actions by non-state actors pose significant challenges, impacting the efficiency and effectiveness of law enforcement bodies. This study employs a descriptive research approach and secondary sources to analyze modern security dynamics and the roles of law enforcement agencies in addressing these challenges. It aims to offer future-oriented strategies for both domestic and international security agencies amidst evolving global security concerns.

Keywords: Challenges; Era; Institutions; Paramilitary; Security

1. Introduction

"Security, as President Lennart Meri eloquently put it, is comparable to virginity: it's binary—you either possess it fully or you do not at all" (Kaljurand, 2012). This analogy underscores the impossibility of partial security and emphasizes the necessity for every state to pursue comprehensive security measures. Former Estonian President Lennart Meri's quote aptly captures the essence of security, acknowledging that no state can assert absolute security because such a state does not exist. Therefore, no state should settle for partial security. Consequently, every nation, irrespective of size, requires a strategic approach to ensure the security of its citizens (Kaljurand, 2012). The security of the citizens is taken as the responsibility of the government.

Security encompasses a range of dimensions focused on safeguarding against harm or ensuring 'freedom from threat'. This prompts inquiries into the nature of security itself—what it signifies, who requires it, and who assumes the role of ensuring it. Security concerns revolve around safeguarding both the state and its populace. The state assumes the responsibility of providing security against internal and external threats. Without adequate security measures, a nation remains susceptible to various dangers, highlighting the critical necessity of protecting lives and property for any prosperous country (Iregbenu & Uzonwanne, 2015). Security, in its broadest context, refers to the extent of resilience and defense against potential harm or peril (Baral & Shah, 2018). Law enforcement agencies are designated entities responsible for safeguarding both the state and its populace. These agencies are tasked with identifying potential threats to the lives and property of individuals, which the state is obligated to protect and ensure. Security agencies play a crucial role in ensuring adherence to specific laws and regulations within a defined territorial jurisdiction, state, or nation.

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Indeed, security agencies play a pivotal role in upholding the laws within any state. Threats present significant challenges to the integrity of the state. The traditional Westphalian concept of security, which primarily focused on safeguarding the state itself, is commonly referred to as the conventional notion of security. However, the emergence of numerous threats that cannot be resolved through military means has prompted scholars to question and broaden this traditional understanding. They advocate for a broadened concept of security that includes not just protection via harm of the body as well as the overall better condition of the people and the ecological sound position of the planet (Dokiubo, 2010, and Ngwube, 2013). An accountable and responsible nation has a duty to improve the personal safety of everyone, regardless of whether they are within its borders or beyond.

In the modern era, academic research and scholarly writings in security studies have increasingly turned their focus towards armed conflicts and internal societal issues within states. These include ethnic conflicts, regionalism, movements advocating for secession, armed resistance, civil wars, and insurgencies. In 1996, United Nations Secretary-General Boutros Boutros-Ghali noted that globalization was fostering a world that is progressively interconnected, serving as a catalyst for positive developments such as decolonization, effective governance, enhancement, rights and security, as well as environmental protection (Manwaring, 2011). The Secretary General also recognized that deformation had been exerting the detrimental influence, prompting individuals worldwide to seek solace in smaller factions marked by isolationism, separatism, extremism, and an increase in conflicts within states (Manwaring, 2011). Consequently, advancements in science and technology have continuously reshaped people's living standards. Moreover, the worldwide form of business and economy have fostered through modern technological progress as well as inter connectedness in many nations including societies. In the current era, security threats prompt considerations about safeguarding state authority from intricate internal dynamics, with citizens comprising this authority. Law enforcement agencies, entrusted as guardians of the state, bear the responsibility of shielding people from harm and preserving peace and stability within their borders. A fundamental objective of these agencies is ensuring the protection of the country and its populace. However, threats of applying the law at the time involve identifying significant deficiencies that render society susceptible to social crimes, thus threatening internal security. This article emphasizes key challenges of the modern era and explores inquiries into contemporary security concerns. It examines global trends among international law enforcement agencies in addressing these challenges, as well as the mechanisms and initiatives devised by states to combat security threats. By reviewing various studies on current security issues and the roles of law enforcement agencies, this article aims to assist these agencies in mitigating persistent security threats and exploring innovative approaches practiced by some agencies to enhance internal security and mitigate societal risks.

Samuel and Sharma (2016) highlighted the pivotal role of technology in enabling various societal functions. They noted that terrorists have access to technologically advanced tools such as the worldwide condition of the tools of sketching through the net and exploring the earth through the internet, which allow them to access of the picture's trough satellite become the goal. This represents an important evolution of the then times. They also noted that ISIS has a significant sight across various social networks and the platforms. The 2008 Mumbai terrorist attacks served as a critical alert for global law enforcement agencies, revealing new security challenges. In response, the United States has allocated substantial resources and coordinated intelligence and law enforcement efforts to counter terrorist networks. Furthermore, US military strategy involves strengthening the forces of the military of the government in Iraq, who have been actively fighting against ISIS. Indelle and Cadier (2013) highlighted that terrorists' activities have emerged as the foremost threat of the security in international level, shifting from national concerns to a global issue with widespread impact. Regarding counter terrorism efforts, three main strategies are outlined.

The first approach, prevalent in Europe, focuses on policing and intelligence, drawing parallels with criminal activities. The second approach emphasizes long-term strategies, while the third adopts a military perspective involving the use of force and preemptive actions. Migration poses significant threats and impacts national and international security in three main ways, according to Indelle and Cadier (2013). Firstly, it affects state capacity and autonomy. Secondly, it influences power dynamics among states. Lastly, it alters the nature of violent conflicts. Migration poses risks as organized crime networks exploit migratory flows for human trafficking profits, and terrorist networks exploit them to access target states. These are the different researchers' concepts of the security threats in the world.

Security challenges has become one of the most complicated subjects it Nepal and it is as hard as Adhikari et al (2020) have claimed in keeping the ecology and the environment of the world in a balanced form for security of humanity and it is as complex as Adhikari et al (2022) have discussed about the global condition of the system of the government and it has turned out as beyond the control as Adhikari (2020) has analyzed about the existing condition of the world's deteriorating system of the environment and ecology due to the governments of the world. However, the security has to be enhanced and managed in the legal provision and it has to be brought in the practical affairs of life in each and every sectors. But the researchers have not brought the way of enhancing the condition of the security challenges in Nepal and the mechanism of strengthening the legal provision to include the security strategies in every task in the

country properly and effectively for the overall development of the administrative reformation of the security yet. It has become one of the most complicated tasks in enhancing the security as Adhikari, (Academia. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.25058/179400x.1709>) has discussed about the difficulties of transforming from one religion to another one in his "Fear in Religion." The enforcement of law for the solution of the security challenges and its use in the target of mitigating the goal has to be explored and applied it as the requirement of the society.

1.1. Statement of Problems

The various researchers have attempted to explore the security threats but they have not focused the principle of the law enforcement and its situation. The research has attempted to fill the gap by answering the following research questions.

- What are the present security challenges increasing day to day?
- How can the present challenges be addressed by the enforcement of law?

1.2. Research Objectives

The present world has turned out as one small village and the security issues have been increasing day to day with the advancement of technology and information. So, the main objectives of the research are to answer the aforementioned research questions. The research has focused:

- To identify the present security challenges increasing day to day.
- To explore the ways of the present challenges to be addressed by the enforcement of law.

2. Methodology

This research employs a descriptive research methodology and relies on secondary sources to investigate modern security challenges and international efforts to mitigate them. It focuses on significant internal security issues faced by states and examines strategies and developments aimed at combating these threats. The study scrutinizes state mechanisms and initiatives designed to address contemporary security challenges, including policies, planning processes, legal frameworks, security arrangements, and regional and global cooperation among states. Furthermore, it utilizes discourse analysis to assess the practices adopted by law enforcement agencies. Based on this analysis, the paper concludes by evaluating the role and effectiveness of law enforcement agencies in the contemporary era.

3. Results

3.1. Conceptual Clarification of Security: Exploring Definitions, Dimensions, and Contemporary Relevance

The term "security" originates from the Greek word "se-cura," which means "to be in a state of no fear" (Kasali, 2011, p. 19). While the concept of security is subject to debate, security scholars generally agree that it pertains to safeguarding human life from threats by any means. As human society has evolved, different approaches to security have emerged, including traditional security, human security, and collective security. Traditional security, often referred to as conventional security, encompasses historical perspectives on security issues. Traditional security, also known as national security, pertains to protecting a nation from external threats that endanger its sovereign existence as an independent state. It emphasizes the primacy of state interests and the security of its people, viewing military strength as indispensable for survival. In the context of internal security, Mijah (2007) defines it as ensuring freedom from factors that could undermine national cohesion and threaten the existence of essential institutions. This includes safeguarding core values, socio-political and economic objectives, and meeting the legitimate aspirations of the population. Moreover, internal security involves safeguarding lives and property while creating conditions that allow individuals to continue in their legal interests in the society to society themselves (Imobighe, 1990). Historically, security studies concentrated on national interests and sovereignty within the framework of realpolitik in international relations, influencing national policy. However, as human society has evolved, new theories and principles in security studies have emerged, shifting from a narrow focus on realpolitik to a more comprehensive view of global security as an interconnected whole.

3.2. Emerging Threats to Global Security and Paradigm Shifts and Future Challenges

The protection condition can be defined as a particular understanding of the conservation of environment within the social structures, characterized by specific trends and concerns. It is widely acknowledged that security has become a topic of increasing interest among scholars in the social sciences, encompassing a diverse range of issues. Research in this field has yielded new insights and discoveries, highlighting a noticeable shift in how security is perceived and

discussed (Kasali, 2011). The concept of a security paradigm draws from various origins, reflecting the distinct security landscapes of different regions. For instance, the security dynamics in Middle Eastern countries differ significantly from those in West African states. Historically, the Westphalian notion of security focused on state-to-state aggression as the primary threat (Kasali, 2011). Prior to World War II, the main threat to a state's sovereignty generally came from other states (Kasali, 2011). However, after the second World War, the focus of the protection began to shift towards the protection and well-being of individuals and groups, with states taking on the responsibility for their citizens' security and development. From the beginning of the cold war, the major threats to state security have evolved, with increased attention to internal issues such as insurgencies and civil conflicts affecting nations worldwide (Kasali, 2011). The escalation of internal conflicts in the developing world during the 1990s led to a reevaluation of how development and insecurity are interconnected (Smith 2001; Woods 2005; Swiss, 2011). The concept of human security has expanded to include a wider range of concerns, shifting the focus from traditional state-centered security to the security of individuals. This evolution has increased interest in the political activities, economic acts, dynamics of power, the management of the resources, as well as the role of actors of out the nation in homeland affairs.

These developments have introduced numerous challenges for both states and populations at large. For instance, Southeast Asia's security landscape has been influenced by fast transformation of economy, factual as well as possible disease outbreaks, and increasing common interests and grievances among Islamic communities in the region (Ott, 2006). Such interest can be much more hazardous than anything else.

3.3. Navigating Modern Security Landscapes

In today's globalized world, the nature of threats is continually changing, driven by the widespread use of information technology. When addressing modern security issues, I find it useful to reference the insights of the ancient strategist Sun Tzu. He noted that as circumstances evolve, so too do the nature of threats. He stressed the need to adjust strategies to meet new kinds of adversaries, who are often elusive, ideologically motivated, and avoid traditional combat, presenting unprecedented challenges (Rice, 2006). In the post-Cold War era, small states in South Asia have increasingly attracted the attention of external actors due to ideological disputes among regional powers and a lack of regional cohesion. This shift has amplified security concerns in these countries, mirroring broader geopolitical trends and the complexities of contemporary security environments.

Baral and Shah (2018) discuss various global challenges such as the spread of nuclear weapons, the rise of Islamic fundamentalism, armed conflicts, separatist movements, and political transformations impacting the world today. They highlight the emergence of ISIS as a particularly brutal terrorist organization using new tactics to instill fear and vulnerability, especially in smaller and developing countries. Groups like Al-Qaeda and Jemaah Islamiyah are noted for their readiness to commit symbolic crimes targeting significant social or cultural symbols (e.g., the Pentagon), disruptive acts like bombings of transportation and nightlife venues, and spectacular crimes combining both types (Baral & Shah, 2018, p. 5). In this contest, Adhikari et al (2022) have argued that the security of the global citizens can be maintained only through the formation of the international government of UN as the whole world taking as one nation. In fact, the global crimes can be controlled by the global joint act.

The tactic of using suicide bombers has gained popularity among jihadist Islamic groups, posing significant security threats in European, South Asian, and West Asian countries. This trend suggests that certain groups may sponsor these threats, complicating efforts by security forces to identify and apprehend terrorists. Suicide bombing presents a complex challenge, with attacks increasing dramatically over recent decades. While there were few incidents in the 1980s and a slight rise in the late 1990s, the number surged attacks (Atran, 2006; Moghadam, 2008; Irondelle & Cadier, 2013). Contemporary terrorist violence often results in relatively low perpetrator participation but causes extensive casualties, fostering violence, hatred, and enmity. Even small-scale attacks may serve as rehearsals for larger, more destructive assaults in the future, as extremists continually refine their skills in the engineering of the explosive forms (Noor, 2015). In recent decades, the European Union (EU) has encountered major challenges due to chaos and war in neighboring regions, including Libya, Syria, the Sahel, and Ukraine. The security landscape has been further complicated by additional factors such as the 2008 economic and financial crises, the eurozone crisis from 2011 to 2013, immigration without permission non-EU nations, attacks of the terrorists, and the ongoing warning of Muslims' terrorism. The increasing incidence of suicide terrorism in conflict-ridden areas like Iraq, Syria, Afghanistan, and Libya has also intensified the EU's security concerns.

3.4. International Strategies and Practices in Combating Contemporary Security Challenges

Contemporary security scholars highlight the increasing importance of arming security agencies with advanced weaponry, technology, intelligence capabilities, and tailored training to address rising internal threats within societies. Nations are now focusing on innovative security approaches and advocating for interconnected structural power that

has become versatile and functioning (Gandhi, 2015). Traditionally, top high decorating involved covert intelligence gathering by security services to preempt threats, while low policing focused on overt methods by public police to disrupt criminal activities (Brodeur, 2007). The police force is always in the process of controlling the crimes and the criminal activities.

The armed forces are categorized into three distinct groups: the military component, which comprises the active-duty forces; the auxiliary component, which includes support and non-combat units; and the reserve component, consisting of individuals who can be called upon to serve in times of need. The global increase in the armed forces reflects increasing threats and challenges driven by changing global dynamics. The international security environment greatly influences domestic security, especially with issues like international terrorism and transnational organized crime, which blur the lines between internal and external threats (Lutterbeck, 2013). Given the evolving security landscape and the complex nature of contemporary threats, there is a need for strong armed security agencies. These agencies, which include entities such as India's paramilitary forces, Europe's gendarmerie, and Nepal's Armed Police Force, function similarly to military units but with a law enforcement focus. Their effectiveness in addressing modern security challenges highlights their crucial role in managing current threats (Lutterbeck, 2013). In Australia, legislative reforms since 2001 have significantly expanded the Australian Federal Police (AFP) in terms of size, scope, and responsibilities. These changes have increased the AFP's powers, improved its counter-terrorism capabilities, and integrated its functions with those of state and territory police forces, which handle the majority of criminal law enforcement (Ransley & Mazerolle, 2009; AFP, 2017). Police agencies are classified according to their particular roles in managing security concerns, with their functions adjusted to the types of threats they encounter. Security policy analysts anticipate that non-state actors will play a growing role in influencing global dynamics in the future (Hauser, 2007).

Establishing specialized police forces with training to confront modern security challenges is considered crucial. Such security agencies are often referred to as paramilitary, blending police and military roles. Auten (1986) defines paramilitary as organizations that either operate alongside or cooperate with a country's official armed forces, adopting military tactics and organizational structures for non-military purposes (Auten, 1986). The governmental military forces have to be strong enough in exploring the possible criminal activities.

3.5. The Evolution and Impact of the US Department of Homeland Security

In the wake of the attacks September 11 in Twin towers in New York, the United States advocated a worldwide anti-terrorism campaign, which combined the military operations like the intervention in Afghanistan to dismantle the Taliban and eliminate Al Qaeda. Another key development was the creation of the US Department of Homeland Security, which restructured federal agencies (Ackleson & Heyman, 2010). The 9/11 commission highlighted the inadequate support within the intelligence agencies of the government as a critical shortcoming (Eldridge et al., 2004; Warner, 2010). Intelligence agencies need to improve their responsibility in timely identifying threats to national security and the safety of citizens.

According to Warner (2010), the United States was unprepared to respond to a major terrorist attack due to inadequate coordination among intelligence agencies and law enforcement. In reaction, the Homeland Security Act of 2002 brought about major organizational changes within the US government, including the creation of the Department of Homeland Security and the reorganization of intelligence agencies under the National Counterterrorism Center (Warner, 2010). Prior to the 9/11 attacks, the US-Canada border was commonly known as the "longest undefended border" globally. However, following 9/11, armed police and paramilitary organizations began patrolling this border, marking a dramatic shift in security measures (Wintendyk & Sundberg, 2010, Warner, 2010). The security measures have shifted and it has become more challenging with the advancement of the technology.

3.6. The Role and Impact of the Canadian Border Services Agency (CBSA) on National Security and Border Management

The Canadian government introduced various strategies to prevent and address the issue of "irregular migrants" attempting to enter or remain in the country (Aiken, 2006). In a development akin to the establishment of the U.S. Department of Homeland Security, Canada set up the Canadian Border Services Agency, which consolidated previously separate customs, immigration, and food inspection roles. This agency became the principal authority for monitoring and securing Canada's borders (Warner, 2010). Additionally, Canada has invested in resources aimed at intercepting irregular migrants to thwart the entry of individuals who might pose terrorist threats (Aiken, 2006; Warner, 2010). To further enhance its counter terrorism efforts, Canada also passed the Anti-Terrorism Act in 2001.

The Canadian Anti-Terrorism Act aims to effectively prevent, prosecute, and penalize terrorist activities and organizations within Canada. In 2006, the Canadian government allocated \$101 million to enhance the capabilities of

4,800 border services officers by providing them with equipment such as ballistic vests and handguns, effectively elevating their role to a paramilitary status (Warner, 2010). The Canadian Border Services Agency is tasked with ensuring thorough border security throughout Canada. It collaborates closely with international partners to adopt best practices and has created its own training materials for other administrations. The agency is also globally recognized for its specialized training centers, which provide expertise in areas such as marine operations, border services officer recruitment, detector dog programs, and forensic sciences (CBSA, 2014). This has made it a key player in aligning skills and technology with international standards.

3.7. European Union Security Challenges and Responses

Prior to 2001, the European Union had no a unified explanation of terrorists' activities or standardized punishment (Warner, 2010). However, after the September 11 attacks, there has been ongoing discussion about state foreign and security policies. Biscop (2008) notes that the EU's foreign policy did not significantly shift after 9/11, nor did it change much after the violent attack in Madrid in March 2004 and London in July 2005. Also, the powers military force within the Europe recognizes the limitations of tackling global security challenges on their own. Although there is a strong case for collective action, the EU has struggled with achieving cohesive responses (Chappell, Mawdsley & Petrov, 2016). The evolution of gendarmerie forces within the European Union (EU) is evident in their significant growth since the 1990s and their increasingly crucial role in addressing diverse contemporary security challenges. These challenges include responsibilities such as managing borders, countering terrorism, and engaging in international peacekeeping operations (Lutterbeck, 2013). In France, internal security is overseen by two main police forces: the national police, which operates under civil law and is managed by the Ministry of security functions as a military police force under the Ministry of Defense (Vitkauskas, 1999). Additionally, the European Gendarmerie Force (Eurogendfor), also known as the Carabinieri, acts as a paramilitary organization with military status. This force is essential for maintaining security, delivering justice, and addressing threats and risks in complex scenarios involving transnational terrorism, organized crime, and emergencies.

3.8. Role and Evolution of the Indian Parliament

In India, all states operate their own police force according to the constitutional framework. The government of the center has the power to create and organize forces for national defense and territorial integrity (Mishra, 2015). Since 1979, India has established various paramilitary forces. The central reserve police force was originally formed during British colonial rule in response to civil unrest that the British Indian Army found challenging to manage during the freedom movement. Over time, the CRPF has been actively involved in various operational activities, particularly in counterinsurgency efforts, and played a significant role during the 1965 conflict in Rann of Kutch. Following the Rann of Kutch conflict, the Border Security Force (BSF) was established to protect India's borders. The BSF is outfitted with modern weaponry and undergoes extensive training and education (Mishra, 2015). Additionally, the Indian Coast Guard was created in 1976 under the Ministry of Home Affairs to defend India's extensive 3,400-mile coastline and its territorial waters.

Various paramilitary forces in India, including the ITBP, BSF, and Assam Rifles, were established to address issues related to counter-terrorism, border security, and internal violence. Specifically, the ITBP was founded in 1962 to protect the India-China border in Tibet, while the BSF was created in 1965 to secure the India-Pakistan border. The National Security Guard (NSG), formed in 1986, is a specialized commando force designed to tackle serious terrorist threats. The ITBP and the Sashastra Seema Bal (SSB) are responsible for the security of the Indo-Tibetan, Indo-Nepal, and Indo-Bhutan borders, respectively. The Central Industrial Security Force (CISF) is charged with safeguarding major airports, metro stations, nuclear sites, and around 200 Public Sector Undertakings (PSUs) across the country. The NSG, equipped with two strike and three support battalions, is strategically deployed to handle internal security crises efficiently. The NSG's successful management of the 2008 Mumbai terrorist attack on the Taj Hotel underscores its proficiency in crisis response.

3.9. The Role and Evolution of Indonesian Paramilitary Forces

In Indonesia, a specialized paramilitary unit with 12,000 members was established to focus on internal security and defense duties (Dillon, 1997). Despite the Indonesian National Police being the second largest police force in the world after the army, its main function is to serve as the regular police force responsible for general security. The Indonesian security framework is distinctive, involving four agencies under the Armed Forces of the Republic of Indonesia (ABRI), which performs dual roles. ABRI encompasses the army, air force, and police, with the army playing a dominant role (Dillon, 1997). Furthermore, the Indonesian National Counter Terrorism Agency, created in 2010, actively contributes to the country's counterterrorism efforts.

3.10. Role and Evolution of the Armed Police Force in Nepal

In reaction to changing global security trends and the rise of unconventional threats, the Nepalese government set up the Armed Police Force (APF) in 2001. The APF's motto, "Peace, Security, and Commitment," reflects its readiness to handle "Any Task, Any Time, Any Place." Initially created during the Maoist insurgency, the APF has since taken on a wide range of responsibilities. Before its formation, internal security in Nepal was managed primarily by the Nepal Police and the National Investigation Department. The APF was set up to tackle modern security issues, including terrorism, insurgency, cross-border crime, riots, and other threats. Today, the Armed Police Force, Nepal is tasked with thirteen key responsibilities related to internal security, such as border control, counterinsurgency, managing armed conflicts, fighting separatist movements, riot management, VIP/VVIP protection, and industrial security. With approximately thirty-seven thousand personnel, the APF is equipped to handle disaster management, industrial security, revenue protection, and customs security effectively in Nepal.

3.11. The Role and Effectiveness of Intelligence Institutions in Safeguarding Intra Protection

Security operations are heavily dependent on intelligence, which plays a crucial role in maintaining internal security for any nation. Intelligence agencies are vital for protecting state security amid the complex and unpredictable nature of non-traditional security threats. Countries use a range of both overt and covert methods for intelligence gathering. For example, in France, the Directorate for Territorial Surveillance (DST) is responsible for domestic security intelligence, including foreign intelligence gathering. The United Kingdom's domestic security intelligence is managed by the British Security Service, known as MI5, while foreign intelligence is conducted by the British Secret Intelligence Service (SIS or MI6). In the United States, the Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI) oversees domestic security intelligence, while the Central Intelligence Agency (CIA) is responsible for foreign intelligence (Vitkauskas, 1999). The successful operation against Osama bin Laden, which involved the tracking and acquisition of critical information by special forces like the Marine Commandos, illustrates the significant impact of intelligence operations on national security.

4. Discussion

Identifying the roots of security threats is crucial, as failure to do so can pose significant challenges for security agencies. However, advancements in law enforcement are creating new opportunities to effectively address these challenges. Many countries worldwide have established armed forces specifically tailored to combat contemporary security threats. Policing has traditionally focused on crime control and democratic principles, but the complexities of modern security threats require additional measures beyond traditional law enforcement. The emergence of agencies like the APF has proven effective in tackling these contemporary challenges. As a result, international trends are increasingly emphasizing the empowerment of armed police and paramilitary auxiliary agencies. These agencies receive specialized training, access to advanced weaponry, and logistical support to enhance their contributions to national security. Simultaneously, states are enhancing their intelligence agencies to gather critical security information and mitigate threats.

Their role involves actively gathering information on various security issues that directly or indirectly threaten national security, both internally and externally. According to Hans J. Morgenthau, "the armed strength and potential threat are paramount factors determining a nation's political power" (Troxell, 2008, p. 209). This underscores the shift in international practices towards auxiliary and paramilitary security agencies capable of military-like actions in response to today's complex security landscape. Similarly, intelligence agencies play a crucial role in internal security, offering comprehensive oversight against activities detrimental to national interests and social order

5. Conclusion

Modern security faces vulnerabilities due to various negative aspects of globalization, such as state inter dependencies, transnational criminal and militant activities, sectarian politics, the impact of non-state actors on domestic affairs, and global terrorism. These unconventional security threats pose significant risks to people's lives today. Some states are found to be more exposed to these threats due to their geographical and geopolitical positions. To effectively combat these challenges, law enforcement agencies must operate with high efficiency. In the 21st century, law enforcement agencies, particularly those with a paramilitary nature resembling military units, are proving more effective in addressing contemporary security challenges. Likewise, intelligence agencies are essential in assisting the enforcement bodies of law with the operations protection and other activities for maintain the peace.

In response to the 9/11 attacks, the United States established the Department of Homeland Security, a new agency designed to tackle evolving security challenges. Similarly, Canada and the European Union have also restructured their

enforcement bodies of law and identified new methods to address emerging warning and fear. Globally, many nations have been found to have developed new security strategies focused on border security to counter extremism, transnational crime, and other significant threats to national security. The effectiveness of internal security depends on the collaborative efforts of all state security agencies in addressing these challenges.

Learning from international practices is crucial for law enforcement agencies in the current context to effectively combat contemporary security challenges. Ultimately, the long-term security, peace, and resilience of a nation has found to depend on its security policies. Therefore, it is imperative to formulate a comprehensive security policy that prioritizes safety, rule of law, and upholds the human rights and fundamental freedoms of its people.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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